
MORAL AND EDUCATIONAL VALUES OF FAIRY TALES

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Abstract.

Fairy tales help people understand and navigate the world. Fairy tale animation helps people develop a subjective perspective of the real world and living things. By defining meaningful images for the child and thoroughly describing the dynamics of development with the aid of expressive storytelling techniques, the tale helps preschoolers perceive good and evil in the right ways. Within the parameters of mental health, the child's personality develops properly.

Keywords.

folklore, fairy tales, magic items, moral, educational value, child development, cognitive development.

Children can learn about their surroundings through the entertaining medium of fairy tales, improving their comprehension of their surroundings. To breathe new life into the material being studied, fairy-tale modes of perception work to insert an unusual circumstance. Teachers discover ways to reveal the emotional spheres of children with the aid of fairy tale images. Children listen to fairy tales, learn to worry about heroes, solve seemingly difficult tasks, learn to reason, give reasons for their actions and build logical chains.

With their funny and witty lead characters, cognitive fairy tales are fascinating tales that help you form a field of knowledge and gain more understanding of the phenomenon or subject being studied. A cognitive fairy tale's plot details situations that call for reason, research into the issue at hand, and the development, validation, or denial of a hypothesis. A preschooler can learn about the world around him in a laid-back setting thanks to the close connections between the adventures of the heroes and the real world found in all of the cognitive fairy tales.

When planning lessons for preschoolers that include educational fairy tale material, it is important to make sure that the fairy tales encourage the child to participate in the activity. Preschoolers should demonstrate an interest in actively

participating in the event rather than just listening passively. Children learn about logical reasoning in these classes and how to establish the order of events in a fairy tale, both of which are necessary in real life.

K.S. Aksakov believed that "a fairy tale is an epic work of a prosaic, magical, adventurous or everyday character, presented by the author and perceived by the listener as fiction."³⁰⁴ Children in preschool learn about their environment and create their own artwork based on what they see. This knowledge is difficult to comprehend without specialized training, harmful to children's cognitive development, and can be destabilizing to mental health. The child's position in relation to the outside world is unclear. This problem is aggravated in the absence of the proper amount of knowledge, lack of life experience of the child, and insufficient development of the logical thinking of children. A fairy tale is a form of mythological thinking that contributes to solving this problem.

By using metaphorical forms, children can use fairy tales to illustrate theories about the way the world works. Conceptions of good and evil, generosity and greed are built³⁰⁵. The problem of uncertainty is being solved. Children gain planning and event outcome prediction skills. The child overcomes the issue of uncertainty and establishes norms of behavior with the aid of the mythologically inspired reconstruction of the world. Fairy tales help people understand and navigate the world. Fairy tale animation helps readers become more subjective to the outside world and living things.

Preschoolers have a significant difference in their physical and mental capabilities when compared to preschoolers in the middle groups by the sixth year of their lives. In the older group, they are stronger, physically more enduring. As before, there is a connection between the development of intellectual and physical characteristics. Preschoolers' successful multifaceted development against their background is primarily characterized by the development of physical abilities. A big breakthrough is taking place in social formation. The intellect, high morality of the child, his aesthetic self develops. Preschoolers' speech abilities advance, conversational literacy emerges, and their vocabulary is greatly increased.

A characteristic feature of the development of an older preschooler is the development of new skills and knowledge, the personal sides of a preschooler are formed: morality, emotionality, strong-willed, effective practicality, intellectuality. Children learn to follow social norms and submit to authority figures by the time they are six years old. Openly and consciously, emotion is expressed. When

³⁰⁴ <https://gigafox.ru/en/preryvanie-beremennosti/chem-otlichaetsya-skazka-ot-byliny-raznica-mezhdu-bylinoi-i/>

³⁰⁵ <https://edubirdie.com/examples/greed-good-or-evil/>

speaking, the child prioritizes interaction with the other person and expresses interest in the other person. Older preschoolers are able to analyze the speaker's behavior and make clear distinctions between what they like and dislike about him. The ability to reflect on one's actions and deeds develops in children as young as six. A little later, self-esteem develops fully.

A preschooler's moral qualities and behavior expectations specific to the group they are a part of at a given time are how they express their self-esteem. Self-esteem is a state of demonstrated abilities, confirmed by their practice. Each activity that a preschooler learns is understood by the child because of the presence of self-esteem, the desire to stand out from the peer group, and the desire to comprehend the essence of the surrounding events. Every child should pass through this stage of developing the quality of reflection in order to succeed in the school readiness program and advance to a new phase of childhood.

Socialization, which is expressed through the process of cognition and the development of human abilities as a component of society, is a crucial component in the development of older preschoolers. The process of socialization helps an individual survive.

Nikandrov N.D., together with Gavrov S.N., came to the conclusion that the socialization of the child occurs due to the versatile and multifaceted impact of existence, with the help of which the individual learns the rules of "games" adopted in society, approved by this society and confirmed on practice.³⁰⁶ The judgment about the individual is formed on the basis of publicly available measures of society.

As the beginning of the educational process for the burgeoning generation, preschool education in the modern era has legal status. Preschool teachers should work to instill a sense of patriotism in their students while also nurturing their early creativity and intellectual development.

The primary issue with the initial diagnosis of the cognitive development of older preschoolers must be brought to light. The final phase of education before entering school should focus on corrective and developmental work, as this will demonstrate that a crucial element of the child's development is being observed at its most optimum. Under these circumstances, preventive work will be done to avoid both the spread of false information about the educational process of the school curriculum and potential difficulties for schoolchildren in the process of adapting to a new stage.

³⁰⁶ Gavrov, S. N., & Nikandrov, N. D. (2008). Education in the process of personality socialization. Bulletin of URAO, 5, 21-29.

Children can use metaphorical forms in fairy tales to emphasize theories about the organization of their environment. Ideas of right and wrong, altruism and avarice are developed. It has been determined how to deal with uncertainty. Children gain planning and event prediction skills. The young child overcomes the issue of uncertainty and establishes norms of behavior with the aid of the mythological world he has recreated.

Fairy tales help people understand and navigate the world. Fairy tale animation helps people develop a subjective perspective of the real world and living things. By defining meaningful images for the child and thoroughly describing the dynamics of development with the aid of expressive storytelling techniques, the tale helps preschoolers perceive good and evil in the right ways. Within the parameters of mental health, the child's personality develops properly.

Children are delighted by fairy tales because they teach children to be kind, loving, and optimistic. They also teach children to be wise about what is happening, help them to develop empathy and compassion, and teach them to be merciful to animals. The fairy tales of our people have the power to spark the imagination and mold the social work skills. The first heroes of English fairy tales serve as the first idols for the older preschooler. Children are given roles, are able to comprehend their importance, and develop adult masculinity. The preschooler learns the value of a partner and the value of interaction through theatrical play. They also start to reflect on and analyze the plot, understanding each event.

By instilling moral principles in a child as early as senior preschool age, we can guarantee the development of a future individual who will possess spiritual wealth, true moral virtues, and moral purity. A person who is feeling, thinking, loving, and active and who is prepared for creative activity in any field should be the main goal of upbringing, according to our prioritized priority of universal human values.

Without a doubt, using fairy tales will help students learn English more effectively. The fairy tale, along with any other component of the communicative approach to language learning, will diversify the lessons and enable students to learn the necessary material in a simple and enjoyable manner while honing their language skills. Nevertheless, it recognized that depends on for the use of fairy tales in English study to be effective class structure that is logical.

It is worthwhile drawing the conclusion that, fairy tales are an excellent and valuable resource when learning foreign languages based on the aforementioned information. They are entertaining, compelling, and succinct. Students pick up new

vocabulary, moral principles, and grammar-related skills with their assistance. Fairy tales inspire learning and boost interest to language lessons.

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